

ISSUES OF MODERN HERO CREATION IN THEATER ART

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about reforms in the field of culture, art, music, theater art in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the history of theater art, the development of theater art, and the issues of creating a modern hero in theater art.

Keywords: art, culture, reform, hero, theater, ability, tradition, process management, consciousness, reflection.

On August 3, 2017, the head of our state met with representatives of creative intellectuals of Uzbekistan. On the occasion of the four-year anniversary of this meeting, it is natural that there is a need to reflect on the role of the devotees of the field of literature, art and culture in the development of the new Uzbekistan and their role in the society.

As a person who has gained experience in the field of political processes and state administration, worked selflessly for his country, understood his history deeply and deeply, and is selfless for the future of his country and people, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is his compatriot, the majority of thinkers of the East, why for so many centuries a new Renaissance we do not doubt that he thought about the reasons why creative intellectuals capable of creating did not appear. Of course, his following opinion did not just appear: "It would be true if we say that in modern times, when the glorious power of our people is flourishing, a new renaissance is being laid in Uzbekistan - the Third Renaissance. Because today's Uzbekistan is not yesterday's Uzbekistan. Our nation today is not the nation of yesterday." [1]

The laying of the foundation stone of the Third Renaissance by the head of state in our country began from the beginning of his presidency. On this basis, a more ambitious strategic task was formed - the plan to form a social stratum of creative intellectuals that embodies the spirit of the Renaissance.

The meeting of our President with intellectuals on August 3, 2017 was not just a simple dialogue, but to identify the problems and their solutions in the formation of creative intellectuals specific to the new Uzbekistan, to create the conditions for their rise to high creative levels, to mobilize intellectuals, and to define their main new goals and tasks in the educational revival. was the need for good intentions such as clarification. The urgency of the issue, its inextricable connection with the development of the country, caused this event to be held in a critical spirit. [2] At the meeting, it was noted that the current activity of intellectuals does not satisfy our people, that they lack the spirit of living with new creative ideas and initiatives, that the creative environment seems to have stagnated and stagnated in one place, and that most artists are surrounded by their worries and problems. the causes and roots of serious problems in the field were revealed.

Also, the head of state clarified the historical role of intellectuals in building the foundations of revival in society, noting that cultural and artistic figures are always generators of new ideas for the development of society, and asked the question whether they should inspire people towards noble goals and goals with their works and active citizenship. threw in the middle.

At the same time, the head of state pointed out unpleasant situations such as the fact that in the activities of creative associations and state agencies in the field of culture, the moods of

entrepreneurship, work for the economy, laziness and indifference have appeared, most of them are used to working only by waiting for orders from above, and there is no sense of dedication, initiative and organization in their activities. [3] The artist proved that there is no critical spirit among intellectuals with the age-old axiom that "there is no real creativity where there is no healthy criticism, debate and controversy." One of the biggest issues raised at the meeting was the creation of a modern hero image.

Of course, if we pay close attention to the content and essence of the issues mentioned by the President at the meeting, all of them are related to the virtues of literature, art and culture, such as revitalizing the spiritual life of society, enriching the spiritual world of our people under their influence, and leaving the society and the state as a legacy to good young people. In other words, we are talking about socio-cultural conditions, perspectives and possibilities for the formation of human potential for the Third Renaissance.

The history of the Renaissance consists of the names and legacies of great thinkers. That's why John Fogerty, the famous singer of the USA, was right a thousand times when he said, "A society that produces twice as many lawyers as poets and artists is doomed." [4]

In the four years after that historic meeting, presidential decrees and decisions on the development of art and culture, government decisions were adopted. In particular, according to the decision of the President of November 1, 2017 "On measures to further develop the activities of culture and art organizations, creative associations and mass media, and to create additional conditions for stimulating the work of industry employees", talented people in the fields of culture and art and taking into account the housing needs of promising young people, measures were taken to increase the minimum rates of author's fees for the publication of works of science, literature and art. By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers, the Fund for the Development of Culture and Art was established under the Ministry in order to ensure the accumulation of extra-budgetary funds and income of the institutions of the Ministry of Culture system, to strengthen the material and technical base of the institutions of the Ministry of Culture system and to financially encourage their employees. [5]

On November 28, 2018, the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved by the President's decision. One of the main goals of the concept was to emphasize the priority of culture, to ensure a higher level of the quality of society's life, to achieve the harmony of citizens in it, to form a spiritual, responsible, independent thinking creative person. In general, the concept envisages the development of all aspects of culture and art.

According to the decree of the President of May 26, 2020 "On measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society", the implementation of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the field, the republic's tasks were set to establish theater, museum, mobile circus and zoo activities in all regions, to continue the reforms in the field of culture and art, and to further improve the activities of cultural bodies and institutions.

The legal basis for creating conditions for the development of the sphere of culture and art, giving social and state orders to creative intellectuals was embodied in the decree.

The President's speech at the meeting with representatives of creative intellectuals can be considered as one of the most important directions of the strategy of forming the foundations

of the Renaissance. Cultural and spiritual life could not be allowed to lag behind at a time when the results of deep reforms in the fields of economy, society, and political system were manifesting themselves. That is why the creation of high-level art, literature and culture works of the Renaissance, which are quickly noticeable and have a strong impact on international life, became an important direction of state policy.

No matter how sonorous the word "Renaissance" sounds, human potential and thinking are enough to build it. Because when we say renaissance, first of all, high human values come to mind, such as the ability of a person to demonstrate his freedom and creative potential, to feel that his life is meaningful, to acquire the ability to create works of high art and culture, and to see the enjoyment of his work. In short, renaissance means the awakening of a person and a nation. That's why the head of state began to build the foundations of the Renaissance with zeal and enthusiasm. He is overcoming all obstacles on this path, he sincerely believes in the prospects of the reforms he initiated and is implementing. Of course, these fundamental changes are being implemented, first of all, for the sake of the nation, for its well-being, for its recognition in the world.

Only the implementation of the policy in the field of improving the conditions and activities of creative intellectuals means which way we are going. This path is a completely new stage of development called "New Uzbekistan", a period of laying the foundation stone for the foundation of the Third Renaissance. In other words, introducing new Uzbekistan to the world, entering the era of modern civilization and development of civil society.

Summary. More attention is paid to the composition of the repertoire of the Karakalpak State Academic Musical Theater named after Berdaq and the creative problems of creating the image of the hero of the times. First of all, special emphasis was placed on the history of the formation of professional stage works aimed at forming the idea of national independence in the Karakalpak State Academic Musical Theater named after Berdaq.

Also, the repertoires of national heroes of this theater were analyzed. The historical processes of the image of "Berdaq" in the history of the theater and the creative problems of the director and actor in the staging of stage works and recommendations for their elimination are given.

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